

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D1.10.- Updating the Structure and members of the of the Driving Group (DG), Community of Schools (CoS) and National Coordinators' Board (NCB)

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
project number 101059425

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement of the project 101059425. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DELIVERABLE ID

Deliverable No.	D1.10	Work Package No.	WP1	Task/s No.	Task 1.1 – 1.2
Work Package Title	LET'S CARE: Building up a community				
Linked Task/s Title	<i>T1.1. Driving Group conformation and management</i> <i>T1.2. Build a community of schools: LET'S CARE CoS</i>				
Dissemination level	PU	<i>(PU-Public, SEN-Sensitive)</i>			
Due date deliverable	2024-01-31	Submission date	2024-01-31		
Deliverable name	Updating the Structure and members of the Driving Group (DG), Community of Schools (CoS) and National Coordinators' Board (NCB)				

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DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	2024-01-16	First Draft of the document
0.2	2024-01-19	Second Draft of the document
0.3	2023-01-29	Third Draft of the document
0.4	2023-01-31	Final document

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CoS	Community of Schools
DG	Driving Group
NCB	National Coordinators' Board
PAR	Participatory Action Research
PMAB	Policy Makers Advisory Board
GDC	Gender and Diversity Committee
HUB	On-line platform
FWT	FieldWork Team

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1. Executive Summary

The document presents the update of the different structures foreseen in the LET'S CARE community-building project. A brief presentation of each of them has been included, as well as the commitments they should have and their added value. The specific composition of the members of the Driving Group (DG) and the Community of Schools (CoS) is also set out in the document.

2. Introduction

The LET'S CARE project seeks to link research, technological development, and community innovation to understand how a safe attachment can positively affect early school leaving (ESL) and educational (under)achievement in Europe and improve the caring dimension of education systems. The following sections develop specifically on the community building strategy implemented to guarantee this multi-partner approach, how the links and coordination with the LET'S CARE community are defined and the final conformation, structure and roles of the actors involved.

A **Driving Group (DG)**, a **Community of Schools (CoS)** and a **National Coordinator's Board (NCB)** will be the key groups of actors involved. The continuous communication of these actors will contribute to elaborating a definition of a safe education model that acknowledges the real educational experiences of teachers and students and provides a bottom-up perspective of the caring aspects related to ESL and educational (under)achievement. Additionally, these actors will help establish the community and institutional context to enable the data collection and analysis; the development and diagnosis of intervention tools; and the project's advocacy, awareness, and incidence.

Figure 1. Summary of the LET'S CARE Communities

3. Driving Group (DG)

The **DG** is a body made up of one representative from each project partner to dynamise all the project's tasks and activities and link the consortium vision with the rest of the communities, co-constructing and engaging with all the other relevant actors. Its most important functions are coordinating and articulating the NCB and the CoS, whose main functions are explained below. The DG will also operationalise the Policy Maker Advisory Board (PMAB), facilitating contact with other policymakers at the national, regional, and European levels. In addition, this body will be responsible for ensuring a Participatory Action Research (PAR) methodology. The representativeness of all partners will guarantee fieldwork with a multi-stakeholder vision.

3.1. Structure and composition

The project proposal established that the DG should be composed of at least one representative member per project partner. Accordingly, the DG was formed in December 2022 and is currently composed of 26 members: 14 are full members, and 12 substitutes have been appointed to ensure and facilitate the participation of the different entities in the DG. The full members constitute a gender-balanced group composed of 7 women and 7 men. Including the additional 12 substitutes, the full group of 26 members is composed of 16 women and 10 men. Table 1 shows the members of the DG.

As mentioned above, the DG has been formally constituted and functioning as stipulated in the project since December 2022 (M4). There has only been one replacement of a full member (JEX) due to changes in the partner's team. After the official formation of the DG, it was agreed that the group would virtually convene each 4-6 months to provide strategic inputs for all project activities, supported and dynamised by a Technical Secretary led by CIDALIA. From the beginning of the project to the present (M16), the DG has met on 12 December 2022 and 7 February 2023.

To operationalise the work, the **DG has created a sub-working group called the FieldWork Team (FWT)**, which consists of at least one person from those partners who have to carry out fieldwork, plus Cidalia and Comillas. This DG sub-working group was constituted in February 2023 and since then, it has held a total of 5 meetings: 21 March 2023, 11 April 2023, 17 May 2023, 26 October 2023, and 21 November 2023. These meetings have served to design and co-create all the qualitative research techniques developed in WP3 (T3.1 and T3.3) as well as a space for dialogue, reflection, debate, training, and co-creation. All information in Table 1.

Additionally, all DG members have participated in the two sessions on the PAR approach held on 26 October 2023 and 21 November 2023.

The DG and the DG Fieldwork Team sub-working group is being a space for exchange, co-creation, reflection, dialogue, coordination, and a regular and frequent meeting place for all partners focusing on all issues related to WP1 and WP3.

Nº	PARTNER	NAME/SURNAME TITULAR	NAME/SURNAME SUBSTITUTE	FIELDWORK TEAM
1	COMILLAS	Amaia Halty	Eva Bajo	YES
2	CIDALIA	Nuria Lores	Jesús Migallón	YES
3	FACHHOCHSCHULE VORARLBERG GMBH (FHV)	Florian Maurer	Robin Sifferlinger	NO
4	ISTITUTO COMPRENSIVO DI BOSCOCHIESANUOVA (POLO)	Stefano Cobello	Elena Milli	YES
5	Fundación Promaestro	Jorge Úbeda	Macarena Verástegui	NO
6	TIMELEX	Pieter Gryffroy	Olena Barda	NO
7	CONSEJERIA DE EDUCACIÓN Y EMPLEO - JUNTA DE EXTREMADURA	Miguel Méndez	Adela Rosa Lemus	YES
8	STOWARZYSZENIE ARID	Maciej Dymacz		YES
9	PANEVEZIO RAJONO SVIETIMO CENTRAS (PRSC)	Inga Žilinskienė	Jurgita Vaitiekuniene	YES
10	ZABALA INNOVATION CONSULTING, S.A.	Carolina Simón		NO
11	UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA (UCP)	Pedro Días	Lurdes Veríssimo	YES
12	Akademia Ignatianum Krakowie	Ewa Dybowska	Ewa Sowa-Behtane	YES
13	STICHTING INTERNATIONAL PARENTS ALLIANCE (IPA)	Eszter Salamon	Luca Janka László	NO
14	KITE	Iglika Aleksandrova Angelova	Stella Shipkovenska	YES

Table 1. DG members

3.2. Main tasks

The DG holds the essential task of sharing the project's values with key stakeholders and actors that belong to the LET'S CARE communities, thus taking care of:

- Ensuring a space for participation and decision-making of all the partners about the different community structures of the project.
- Providing strategic inputs for all project activities.
- Incorporating the inputs from CoS representatives and the NCB.
- Training and implementing the PAR methodology in all project activities.

4. National Coordinators' Board (NCB)

A **National Coordinators' Board (NCB)** has been progressively set up from the constitution of the DG in December 2022 (M4) until November 2023, when it was completed with all its members with 2 coordinators per country to ensure effective communication and coordination with the DG.

The main function of this body is to facilitate the fieldwork tasks and develop meaningful relationships between the fieldwork partners and the participants of the LET'S CARE Communities. Information on its membership is provided in Table 2. The first meeting of the NCB was held on 13 December 2023, and the second was held on 22 January 2023. In order to boost its participation and co-creation work on the tasks foreseen in WP3 (T3.3), the NCB will meet again in March 2024 and in June 2024.

4.1. NCB Structure and composition

The NCB facilitates, coordinates and guides the activities of the CoS, empowering stakeholders and giving them management and decision-making capacity. It represents a direct link between the Consortium and the CoS. The NCB is composed of:

- a) A representative of each fieldwork project partner responsible for the pilots in the schools.
- b) A representative of the local/national schools' network for each country. This member can represent public or private organisations or networks impacting several schools and institutions.

The partners select the representatives of the schools' networks according to a few requirements that will enable the project implementation, including:

- Sharing of project values.
- Experience in the educational and research field.
- Commitment to the project's successful implementation.
- Knowledge of the English language.
- Availability to participate in local and European meetings.

The NCB must be a stable reference point at the national level throughout the whole duration of the project and after its conclusion.

The Board is elected every four years. The first representatives are the members of the Consortium and the identified teachers (Table 2):

Nº	PARTNER	NAME/SURNAME	COUNTRY
1	ISTITUTO COMPRENSIVO DI BOSCOCHIESANUOVA (POLO)	Stefano Cobello	IT
2	CONSEJERIA DE EDUCACIÓN Y EMPLEO - JUNTA DE EXTREMADURA	Miguel Méndez	SP
3	STOWARZYSZENIE ARID	Maciej Dymacz	PL
4	PANEVEZIO RAJONO SVIETIMO CENTRAS (PRSC)	Inga Žilinskienė	LT
5	UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA (UCP)	Pedro Días	PT
6	KITE	Iglika Aleksandrova Angelova	BG
7	ISTITUTO COMPRENSIVO 06 - CHIEVO - BASSONA - BORGO NUOVO (VERONA)	Annamaria Maiorano Davide Bruno	IT
8	F. MONTERO DE ESPINOSA	Juan Luis Ortiz Espinosa	SP
9	PANEVEZYS "SALTINIS" PROGYMNASIUM	Reda Maknevičienė	LT
10	COMPLEX SCHOOL AND SPECIAL UNITS IN KRAKÓW	Anna Przetocka	PL
11	COLÉGIO NOSSA SENHORA DO ROSÁRIO	Susana Sousa	PT
12	MUNICIPAL SCHOOL "ST.ST. KIRIL AND METHODY" -MALORAD VILLAGE	Maya Doneva-Markovska	BG

Table 2: NCB members

4.2. Main tasks of the National Coordinators' Board

The main task of the NCB will be:

- Debate, discuss and overview CoS's tasks, such as adaptation of data collection instruments, local adjustments of sampling decisions, PAR methodology implementation, contextual validation of language and translation, etc.
- Set up the most appropriate communication channels with the adherent schools (news, announcements, newsletters, integration with face-to-face meetings, etc.).
- Define characteristics, select and invite new schools to join the Community to contribute to the quantitative data collection.
- Support the members of the CoS, promote and sponsor local/national/European events or seminars and workshops about Safe Education.
- Become a contact point for the Community members at a national level.
- Propose further research within the project's subject.

5. LET'S CARE Community of Schools (CoS)

LET'S CARE **CoS** is a real and virtual network in which the principles of the Safe Education approach are transmitted, implemented and validated through the involvement of teachers, principals, schools and educational institutions. The Safe Education approach developed by LET'S CARE focuses on improving the caring dimension of education to overcome the intergenerational transmission of social exclusion. The Community of Schools creates a European-wide link between teachers who share a common understanding of the importance of preventing exclusion, underachievement, disengagement, and school dropout by creating a safe educational environment for all learners.

The CoS is the backbone of the project and its implementation in educational environments will actively contribute to providing data and co-constructing a wider view and narratives for the design and implementation of the project's activities.

5.1. CoS Structure and composition

LET'S CARE CoS have been formed in 2 main phases. Initially (M1-M4), CoS will be composed of 3 schools from the fieldwork countries (Portugal, Spain, Italy, Bulgaria, Poland and Lithuania). That is called "the seed of the LET'S CARE CoS". In a second phase (M4-M16), the CoS will be expanded to 120 members (at least 20 schools per the 6 previously mentioned countries).

The partners select the representatives of the schools' networks according to a few requirements that will enable the project implementation. In the CoS, the main criterion for inclusion is educational

disadvantage, either at meso (school) or micro (students in the educational community) level. In this sense, in the first phase with the seed of the CoS, as in the case of the NCB, the sampling criterion will be incidental for the same reasons: they are a group of schools that we seek to be active members, identified with the values of the project, and directly concerned by its objectives. As the network of centres expands, these criteria can be made more flexible as long as we are dealing at least with our target group at the micro level.

By the year 2028, the involvement of schools from other countries in the Community of Interest could be expected through collaboration with other community networks that share CoS values (e.g. “Nobody Less”¹).

5.1.1. CoS building strategy

The building up of the CoS is a process that has been implemented in 3 phases:

1) Community of interest: in the project's first phase, partners have presented LET'S CARE project and its aims to several stakeholders. School directors and teachers have informed the partners about their interest in joining the network. This initial group of schools will be introduced to the Safe Education approach and LET'S CARE tools in order to provide them with a clearer understanding of the commitment required by the Community. The Community of Interest is composed not only by teachers but also by people interested in the project's results as stakeholders, professors, researchers, doctors, practitioners in the field of education and psychology, decision-makers, policymakers or representatives of associations and organisations. The Community of Interest is an online space open to discussing the project's topics. General information about the project and its results will be shared in the Community through a mailing list and/or chats. The Community of Interest will support the implementation of the project since it will:

- Contribute to the dissemination of the project.
- Identify participating/piloting schools.
- Engage target groups through discussions and exchanges of opinions.
- Enrich the feedback and the contributions to the Safe Education approach adaptation to the educational context.
- Facilitate the engagement of the members in the Network of Stakeholders.
- Ease the participation of target groups from non-partner countries.

¹Nobody Less is a network of stakeholders (schools, NGOs, etc.) working together for prosocial values. The network was built inside a European project. For more information: <https://nobodyless.org/>

2) Initial Community of Schools (the seed of the CoS): each of the 6 partners involved in the project's piloting phase has selected within the Community of Interest 3 schools/country (18 in total) that will represent the initial core of the CoS (see Deliverable D1.1 table 3). These schools have been directly involved in the project's model validation, qualitative data collection and piloting phases. Teachers and principals of these schools will be trained in Participatory Action Research and LET'S CARE methodologies. The project piloting partners have involved a school of every level of education (pre-school, primary and secondary).

3) Wider Community of Schools: in the following phase (M4-M16), the project's partners have selected new schools for a total of 20 schools per country (120 in total). It is essential to include certain criteria for the selection of schools to match the LET'S CARE objectives. In this sense, the characteristics that the CoS should have, as agreed, and proposed by the DG in the meeting of 12 December 2022, would be:

- Coverage of the different educational levels targeted in the project's implementation (ECEC; Primary; Secondary; Post-Secondary,)
- Coverage of centres geographically sited across different degrees of urbanization (urban, suburban, rural).
- Presence of populations intersected by the targeted axes of disadvantage (ethnicity, especially Roma children, migrant background, low SES, (dis)ability; (non)parental care).

Figure 2: CoS inclusion criteria

These schools will be involved and included in the quantitative data collection. Information on its membership is provided in Table 4.

Figure 3: CoS building phases

5.1.2 Co-creation process with communities

Simultaneously with the development of the NCB and CoS structures, our goal is twofold: firstly, to incorporate their perspectives and insights into the collaborative design of various methodologies for the LET'S CARE project, utilizing a participatory methodological approach (PAR). Secondly, we aim to provide a platform for collective reflection and skill enhancement. To achieve these objectives, we have organized five co-creative workshops focusing on qualitative research techniques involving children and young people. The workshops already carried out at this deliverable submission period have been:

- 13 December 2023: SMAT co-creation workshop with children and young people for the educational community in Italy, 74 participants.
- 18 December 2023: Co-creation workshop on the SMAT technique with children and young people aimed at the training of trainers in Italy. 52 participants.
- 16 January 2024: Co-creation workshop on the Photovoice technique with children and young people aimed at the educational community in Spanish, 18 participants.
- 22 January 2024: Co-creation workshop on the Photovoice technique with children and young people aimed at the educational community in the LET'S CARE project countries in Italian, 62 participants.
- 24 January 2024: Co-creation workshop on the Photovoice technique with children and young people aimed at the educational community in the LET'S CARE project countries in English, 86 participants.

During these workshops, employing a highly participatory methodology, we are actively gathering suggestions, observations, needs, and ideas. This information will play a crucial role in shaping the design of Photovoice and SMAT techniques applied to young people and children in the LET'S CARE

project (WP3 T3.3). Additionally, it will contribute to the collaborative development of tools intended for application in May, facilitating a participatory ethnographic analysis throughout the entire process with various educational communities. Detailed documentation of these workshops is accessible in the events space of the Hub:

Figure 4: Co-creative workshops in the Hub

Additionally, in order to facilitate the concrete participation of the of schools to actively join the Community of schools of the project, it is necessary to boost the teachers’ motivation towards the projects and its values/pillars, to make them feel active contributors to the change within the educational systems proposed by the project’s activities and to let them know that their voice counts at every level.

We aim therefore to create some **Communities of Interests on specific topics** that will become spaces for discussion, co-creation, exchange of good practices, mutual training, and educational areas of expertise with the teachers from all Europe. These thematic communities will engage teachers on the topics that are more directly connected with their reality and the project’s outcomes, enhancing

the level of their participation in the LET'S CARE Safe Education strategies. This process will facilitate the involvement of the schools in the data collection since the teachers will perceive they are receiving as much as they are giving (the data collection will improve their workload; it must be a task worth doing). Every sub-community will have a coordinator, chosen among the project's partners, but all the partners can contribute and have to follow the discussion actively.

As a starting proposal of the partners in charge of the selection of the CoS, 7 thematic sub-communities have been created based on their experience in working with schools and on the themes most in demand by them. These 7 sub-themes will be periodically reviewed and submitted to election by all the CoS once they have been selected. The thematic communities proposed so far are:

1) (Neuro-psycho) Pedagogy for the student's well-being and learning competencies

A space of discussion with materials about the students' needs, their rights, and how to improve the learning motivations and competencies.

[LET'S CARE community for pedagogy](#)

2) Environment for learning / learning for the environment (give a voice to nature)

A space for reflection on how to work with students on these issues, especially important for vulnerable groups, exchange of materials and good practices.

[Let's care LET'S CARE community for the environment](#)

3) Coding, robotics, and game-based learning for inclusive peer-to-peer education pedagogy This space will have an impact on reducing the impact of the digital divide, especially important for vulnerable students.

[LET'S CARE robotics and coding community](#)

4) Bridging school and families: strategies of proper and effective communication

Favouring spaces for communication between schools and families has emerged as a key issue in interviews with schools and families. This group arises from this need.

[LET'S CARE schools and families communication community](#)

5) Internal school relationships, communication, and level of structural organisation (teacher-teacher; teacher-principal; bureaucracy...)

In the interviews with different teachers, the need to have spaces to exchange on these issues has been expressed.

[LET'S CARE community internal school relationships](#)

6) Focus on the learning process: School without marks

In the interviews with different teachers and families, the need to think about how to work on pedagogical tools and values that go beyond the curricular content was mentioned. This space aims to respond to this expressed need.

[Let's care LET'S CARE Community focused on the learning process - schools without marks](#)

7) Focus on vulnerable groups: ethnic minorities, refugees, migrants, and inclusion

As a cross-cutting issue, work with vulnerable groups is essential for the project's objectives. Moreover, the teachers interviewed expressed the need to exchange experiences and good practices in working with these groups.

[LET'S CARE Community on Vulnerable groups](#)

The communities are online, on Viber chats connected to the main chat that we are going to use for the project's Hub. Every project's partner has the task of inviting the teachers to join one or more topic – Community - chats. Viber can automatically translate all the contents of these chats in the user's language, so this will allow overcoming the language barrier. The teachers can decide to be in one or more communities - chat according to their interests. LET'S CARE partners will be present in the chats, moderating and motivating, together with other experts in the field. Within each Community of Interest, there will be chosen and nominated 2 representative teachers who will present the results (or the updates) of the discussions to the main LET'S CARE Hub chat.

More Communities to join

To participate in a community, please update your profile by navigating to "My Account" and selecting the communities you are interested in.

Figure 5: Thematic Communities in the Hub

5.1.3 CoS actual composition

Following the planning of the Let’s Care project, the seed of the CoS has been set up. As seen in Table 3, the CoS is currently composed of 171 schools (51 more than the minimum initially planned because some countries have attracted more schools, as shown in Table 3).

COUNTRY	NUMBER OF SCHOOLS
BULGARIA	20
ITALY	60
LITHUANIA	20
POLAND	27
PORTUGAL	20
SPAIN	24
TOTAL	171

Table 3: Community of Schools (CoS) members per country

The composition of the seed of the CoS is heterogeneous according to the variables established in the section 5.1.1, point 4, CoS inclusion criteria.

In terms of these variables, it can be seen how the levels of education are balanced, which will enrich the analysis to be carried out:

Figure 6: CoS Education level distribution

Due to the geographical location of the schools, 33% rural schools have been included, which is undoubtedly very important in order to reflect this reality:

Geographical situation

Figure 7: CoS Geographical situation

The 171 schools that form part of the CoS are highly heterogeneous in terms of the presence of disadvantaged students, 71% of CoS schools are disadvantaged schools:

DISADVANTAGE TYPE	PERCENTAGE OF SCHOOLS IN THE CoS (%)
Ethnicity, especially Roma children	8,19%
Migrant background	2,92%
(Dis)ability	6,43%
(Non) parental care	1,17%
SES	4,68%
Multiple Disadvantages	48,54%
No specific disadvantaged	28,07%

Table 4: Percentage (%) of disadvantaged Schools (CoS)

5.2. Main tasks of the CoS

The schools that will be part of the community must ensure continuity in participation through a written agreement with the Consortium. The members of the CoS will be considered Pole-schools that will inform other schools in their territory about Safe Education. They will organise or host dissemination events or trainings for other teachers.

The advantages of being part of school in the CoS will be:

- Receive specific training on Safe Teaching and Participatory Action Research to improve the academic results and inclusion of all the students.
- Improve the well-being and the inclusion of the students.
- Understand the dynamics of successful academic results and reduce the drop-out rates.
- Improve teachers' competences, knowledge, skills and motivation, especially about the needs of learners with difficulties and at risk of social and educational exclusion.
- Belonging to a network of support and exchange of safe educational practices.
- Bring prestige to the school by assuming an important social value as innovators.
- Implement new educational strategies and good practices.
- Implement and take advantage of the direct results of the piloting phase.
- Strengthen the collaboration among schools and institutions at the European level.
- Be able to develop, promote and encourage the implementation of quality, sustainable and inclusive educational practices, projects and activities.
- Be involved in dialogue, reflection, cooperation and innovation in the educational field.

Commitments of the CoS members will be:

- Participate in the specific training on PAR and LET'S CARE methodology.
- Participate in the qualitative data collection (initial seed of the CoS).
- Participate in the quantitative data collection.
- Participate in information meetings, training courses online and in presence.
- Be active in the LET'S CARE HUB.
- Be in active communication with the other members of the CoS, promoting dialogue and discussion.
- Involve families of the students.
- Involve the teachers at the school (or at least the 3/4 of them).

- Pilot Safe Education approach.
- Organise/host training events for other schools in the territory.
- Promote and support research, innovation, application and development of methodologies for Safe Education and inclusive teaching.
- Encourage exchanges, dissemination of good practices and all activities aimed at improving inclusive and Safe education.
- Engage the local community in understanding the importance of the Safe Education to tackle the intergenerational transmission of social exclusion.

Annex I: CoS Members

Nº	PERSON'S POSITION	NAME OF THE SCHOOL	EDUCATIONAL LEVEL	COUNTRY	GEOGRAPHICAL SITUATION	DISADVANTAGED SCHOOL	WEBSITE
1	Director	Municipal School "St.St. Kiril and Methody" -Malorad vilage, Borovan Municipality, Vratsa region	Middle school	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	
2	Director	WEDA Privet School - Sofia	Pre-primary to Middle School	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	
3	Director	Municipal School "Stephen Peshev" - Sevlievo	Middle school	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	
4	Director	Municipality School "St.Paisii Hilendarski" - Kyustendil	Pre-primary to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	
5	Director	High School "Vasil Levski" - Sevlievo	Pre-primary to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	
6	Director	Primary school St.Kiril and Methodi"- Rajdavitza village	Primary School	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	
7	Director	Professional Gimnazium "Marin Popov"- Sevlievo	Vocational School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	
8	Director	School of Sports "Vasil Levski" Kyustendil	Vocational School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	
9	Director	SU 68 "Academic Nikola Obreshkov" - Sofia	Pre School to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	68su.org
10	Director	SU10 "Theodor Trayanov" - Sofia	Pre School to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	

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11	Director	139 Middle School "Zahari Krusha" - Sofia	Primary to Middle School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	
12	Director	Middle School "Otets Paisii"- Borovan vilage	Middle school	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	
13	Director	SU "Konstantin Petkanov - Burgas	Pre-primary to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	
14	Director	OU "Vasil Levski " - Knidgovnik vilage - Haskovo	Pre-primary to Middle School	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	https://www.vasillevski.net/
15	Director	Professional Gimnazium for tourizm "Nikola Vaptzarov" - Kyustendil	Vocational School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutobosco.edu.it/
16	Director	OU "Sv.Sv. Kiril I Methodii" - Rupite, Petrich	Pre-primary to Middle School	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	https://www.ic6verona.edu.it/sitoweb/index.php?idpag=1
17	Director	SU 8 "Arseni Kostencev" - Blagoevgrad	Pre-primary to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	https://www.ic6verona.edu.it/sitoweb/index.php?idpag=1
18	Director	SU "Sv.Sv. Kiril I Metodii" - Velingrad	Pre-primary to High School	Bulgaria	Urban	YES	https://www.ic6verona.edu.it/sitoweb/index.php?idpag=1
19	Director	66 DG,"Elitza" - Sofia	Pre-primary	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	https://www.ic6verona.edu.it/sitoweb/index.php?idpag=1
20	Director	OU "Georgi Dimitrov" - Bosilegrad	Pre-primary to Middle School	Bulgaria	Rural	YES	
21	Director	San Mauro School – I.C. Bosco Chiesanuova	Pre-primary and Primary school	Italy	Rural	YES	

D 1.1 Structure and members of the DG, CoS and NCB

22	Head teacher of the school	Primary school Camozzini - I.C. 06 Chievo Bassona	Primary school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.ictoti.edu.it/pagine/scuola-dellinfanzia
23	Head teacher of the school	Primary school Gianni Rodari - I.C. 06 Chievo Bassona	Primary school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icmatteottimane.edu.it/
24	Head teacher of the school	Primary school Vilio - I.C. 06 Chievo Bassona	Primary school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icgiuliocesare.edu.it/plessi/infanzia-cesare-battisti/
25	Head teacher of the school	Primary school Angelo dall'Oca Bianca – I.C. 06 Chievo Bassona	Primary school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icgiuliocesare.edu.it/plessi/infanzia-giulio-cesare/
26	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	IPSAR Luigi Carnacina	Secondary school – VET	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.comprendivomorosini.it/
27	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	IC 12 Stadio	Primary school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icdantealighierivenezia.edu.it/
28	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Il bosco parlante	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icdantealighierivenezia.edu.it/
29	Teacher - reference person for	Susan Isaac	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.scuolelidopellestrina.it/

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	early childhood						
30	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Cesare Battisti	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.scuolelidopellestrina.it/
31	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Giulio Cesare	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icmanin.edu.it/
32	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Armando Diaz	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icmanin.edu.it/
33	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	M.P. Pascolato	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivotrentin.edu.it/
34	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Bruno Munari	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.marconiceggia.edu.it/
35	Teacher - reference person for	Zendrini	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.marconiceggia.edu.it/

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	early childhood						
36	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	San Piero in Volta	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.chioggia4.edu.it/
37	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Tre porti	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.chioggia1.it/
38	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Ca' Savio	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icgrimani.edu.it/
39	Teacher	Angolo azzurro	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icgramscicampalto.edu.it/
40	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	G.Rodari	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icgramscicampalto.edu.it/
41	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	I.Calvino	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icvialesanmarco.edu.it/

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42	Teacher - reference person for digitalisation	Brondolo	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icmatteimeolo.edu.it/
43	Head Teacher	Padoan	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icnievocinto.edu.it/infanzia-di-cinto-caomaggiore/
44	Teacher	Collodi	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icnievocinto.edu.it/s-truttura/giai-di-gruaro/
45	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Arcobaleno	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icnievocinto.edu.it/s-truttura/italo-calvino-infanzia/
46	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Girasole	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icnievocinto.edu.it/s-truttura/alice-guarda-il-mondo/
47	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	'8 Marzo	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.comprensivom.alipiero.edu.it/luoghi?id=807
48	Teacher	Il flauto magico	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.comprensivom.alipiero.edu.it/luoghi?id=809

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49	Teacher	Cinto Cao Maggiore	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.comprensivom.alipiero.edu.it/luoghi?id=813
50	Teacher	Giai di Gruaro	pre-primary	Italy	Rural	YES	https://www.comprensivom.alipiero.edu.it/luoghi?id=811
51	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Italo Calvino	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://icchioggia2.edu.it/struttura/colonia-padovan/
52	Teacher	Alice guarda il mondo	pre-primary	Italy	Rural	YES	https://icchioggia2.edu.it/struttura/colonia-padovan/
53	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Archimede	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivodolo.it/
54	Teacher	Girasole	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivodolo.it/
55	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Primavera	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://comprensivocavarzere.edu.it/pagine/infanzia-2
56	Head Teacher	Arcobaleno	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://comprensivocavarzere.edu.it/pagine/infanzia-2
57	Teacher	Colonia Padovan	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://comprensivocavarzere.edu.it/pagine/infanzia-2

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58	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	Ca' Lino	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.marconiceggia.edu.it/
59	Teacher	Piccole tracce	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.marconiceggia.edu.it/
60	Teacher	Isola del tesoro	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.chioggia4.edu.it/
61	Teacher - reference person for early childhood	C.Collodi	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.chioggia4.edu.it/
62	teacher	Piccoli angeli	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.chioggia4.edu.it/
63	Teacher – reference person for health	Tullio Serafin	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icgiulioesare.edu.it/
64	Teacher	E. Filiberto	primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icgiulioesare.edu.it/
65	Teacher	G.Marconi	midle school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icgrimani.edu.it/
66	Teacher	M.Merlin	primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icgrimani.edu.it/
67	Teacher - reference person for inclusion	Don Milani	primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.icmatteimeolo.edu.it/

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68	Teacher - reference person for adoption	Nicolò De Conti	midle school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivotrentin.edu.it/
69	Teacher - reference person for inclusion	G.Cesare	midle school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivotrentin.edu.it/
70	Teacher - reference person for inclusion	C.Battisti	primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivotrentin.edu.it/
71	Teacher	F.Grimani	primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutobosco.edu.it/
72	Teacher – reference person for school continuity	Visintini	primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.ic6verona.edu.it/sitoweb/index.php?idpag=1
73	Teacher	E.Mattei	midle school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.ic6verona.edu.it/sitoweb/index.php?idpag=1
74	Teacher – reference person for school continuity	E.Toti	Primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivotrentin.edu.it/
75	Teacher	A.Fusinato	Primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivotrentin.edu.it/

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76	Teacher – reference person for inclusion	S.Trentin	Middle school	Italy	Urban	YES	https://www.istitutocomprensivotrentin.edu.it/
77	Teacher – psychomotricist	Sacro Cuore	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	
78	Teacher – headteacher	Pre-school of Nogara	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	www.icnogara.edu.it
79	Teacher	Antonio Bortolani de Tregnago	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	https://ictregnago.edu.it/
80	Teacher – headteacher	Manzoni-IC San Bonifacio	pre-primary	Italy	Urban	YES	www.ic1sanbonifacio.edu.it
81	English teacher	Panevėžio „Šaltinio“ Progymnasium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	NO	https://saltinioproгимnazija.lt/
82	Director	Panevezys District Raguvos Gymnasium	High school	Lithuania	Rural	NO	https://raguvosgimnazija.lt/
83	Director	Panevėzys District Naujamiestis School	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Rural	NO	https://nvmokykla.lt/
84	Deputy director	Panevėzys District Upytes basic School	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Rural	YES	https://upytesmokykla.lt/
85	Director	Panevėzys District Paliuniskio basic School	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Rural	YES	https://www.paliuniskis.panevezys.lm.lt/index.php/lt/
86	Deputy director	Panevezys District Smilgiu Gymnasium	High school	Lithuania	Rural	YES	https://www.smilgiai.panevezys.lm.lt/
87	Director	Panevezys District Paistrys Juozo Zikaro Gymnasium	High school	Lithuania	Rural	YES	http://www.paistriogimnazija.lt/

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88	Director	Panevezys District Dembavos Progymnazium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Rural	NO	https://dembavosprogimnazija.lt/
89	Director	Panevezys District Piniavos School-kindergarten	Pri-primary-Primary school	Lithuania	Rural	NO	https://piniavosdm.jimdofree.com/
90	Deputy director	Panevezys District Krekenavos Mykolo Antanaicio Gymnasium	High school	Lithuania	Rural	NO	https://kmag.lt/
91	Director	Panevezys District Velzys Gymnasium	High school	Lithuania	Rural	NO	https://www.velziogimnazija.lt/index.php/lt/
92	Deputy director	Panevezys District Ramygalos Gymnasium	High school	Lithuania	Rural	YES	https://www.ramygalosgimnazija.lt/news.php
93	Director	Panevezys Rozyno Progymnasium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	NO	https://www.rozyno.panevezys.lm.lt/
94	Primary school teacher	Panevezys Vilties Progymnasium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	NO	https://www.vilties.panevezys.lm.lt/up/en/left/Naujienos/
95	Director	Panevežys Berzu Progymnasium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	YES	https://www.berzu.lt/
96	Primary school teacher	Panevezys Mykolo Krakos Progymnasium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	YES	http://www.karkosm.lt/
97	Deputy director	Panevezys Raimundas Sargunas Sport school	High school	Lithuania	Urban	NO	https://sporto.panevezys.lm.lt/index.php/lt/
98	Director	Ukmergės Silo Progymnasium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	NO	https://silo.ukmerge.lm.lt/
99	Director	Alytaus Dainavos Progymnasium	Primary and Middle school	Lithuania	Urban	NO	https://www.dainava.alytus.lm.lt/advm343/
100	Director	Ukmergės Antano Smetonos Gymnasium	High school	Lithuania	Urban	NO	https://smetonosgimnazija.lt/

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101	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa nr 17 w Krakowie	Primary	Poland	Urban	YES	www.kr.edu.pl
102	Director	Szkoła podstawowa w Pstroszycach Pierwszych	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	www.sppstroszyce.pl
103	Director	Zespół Szkół Secjalnych nr 4 w Krakowie	Primary and secondary	Poland	Urban	YES	http://www.zss4krakow.pl/
104	Director	I Liceum Ogólnokształcące w Limanowej	High school	Poland	Urban	NO	https://www.1lo.limanowa.pl/
105	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa w Tymbarku	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	sptymbark.edu.pl
106	Manager	LO nr XXIV we Wrocławiu	Secondary	Poland	Urban	NO	drukarska.net
107	Vice - director	I Liceum Ogólnokształcące w Rabce	Secondary	Poland	Urban	NO	nowotarski.edu.pl
108	Director	Zespół Szkół nr 1 w Limanowej	Secondary	Poland	Urban	NO	www.zsnr1.limanowa.pl
109	Director	Przedszkole samorządowe w Pstroszczach Pierwszych	Kindergarten	Poland	Rural	NO	www.sppstroszyce.pl
110	Director	Szkoła podstawowa im. M.Kopernika w Dąbrowicy	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	http://spdabrowica.pl/
111	School Psychologist	Szkoła Podstawowa im. J. Rymera w Zabełkowie	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	https://zspzabelkow.krzyzanowice.pl/kontakt/
112	Manager	Szkoła Podstawowa w Trzcianie	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	https://trzcziana.edu.pl/
113	Manager	Szkoła Podstawowa im. Bł. Karoliny Kózkówny w Rozdzielu	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	http://zszrozdziele.pl/
114	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa w Górnice	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	http://www.sp2gorno.wist.com.pl/jsite/

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115	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa w Podłopieniu	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	https://sppodlopien.tymbark.pl/
116	Director	Przedszkole samorządowe w Tymbarku	Pre-primary	Poland	Rural	NO	https://przedszkole.tymbark.iap.pl/
117	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa nr 71 w Krakowie	Primary	Poland	Urban	YES	www.zss14.pl
118	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa w Jaksicach	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	http://szkolajaksice.szkolnastrona.pl/
119	Director	ZS nr 2 w Miechowie	VET school	Poland	Urban	NO	http://zs2miechow.pl/szkola/
120	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa w Bukowskiej Woli	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	http://spbukowskawola.eu
121	Director	Zespół Szkół w Dziaduszykach	Primary	Poland	Rural	NO	http://spdziaduszyce.szkolnastrona.pl/
122	Director	Przedszkole Słoneczko w Toruniu	Pre-primary	Poland	Urban	NO	https://przedszkolesloneczko.com
123	Director	IV Liceum Ogólnokształcące im. Kardynała Stefana Wyszyńskiego	Secondary	Poland	Urban	NO	www.zsnr1.limanowa.pl
124	Manager	Technikum nr 8 we Wrocławiu	Secondary	Poland	Urban	NO	drukarska.net
125	Director	Branżowa Szkoła I Stopnia Specjalna nr 31 W Krakowie	Secondary (VET)	Poland	Urban	YES	www.zss14.pl
126	Director	Szkoła Przystosowująca do Pracy nr 1 w Krakowie	Secondary (special)	Poland	Urban	YES	www.zss14.pl
127	Director	Szkoła Podstawowa nr 131 w Krakowie	Primary	Poland	Urban	YES	kr.edu.pl
128	Director	Colégio de Nossa Senhora do Rosário	Preschool to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://www.colegiodorosario.pt/

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129	English teacher	Agrupamento de Escolas Dr. Manuel Laranjeira	Primary to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://www.aemlaranjeira.pt/
130	Director	Escola Básica Integrada de Rabo de Peixe	Preschool to Middle School	Portugal	Rural	YES	https://www.ebirp.com/portalNew/index.php
131	School Psychologist	Escola Secundária Poeta António Aleixo	Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://www.aepaa.pt/
132	Director	Colégio Camões	Preschool to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://colegiocamoes.com/
133	School Psychologist	Escola Básica do 2º e 3º Ciclo do Caniço	Middle School and Lower Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://escola23canico.com/
134	Teacher	Agrupamento de Escolas de Pedrouços	Primary to Secondary School	Portugal	Rural	YES	https://escolasdepedroucos.com/
135	Co-Director	Colégio Paulo VI	Preschool to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	YES	https://www.colegiopaulovi.com/
136	Director	Colégio do Sardão	Preschool to Primary School	Portugal	Rural	NO	https://www.colegiosardao.org/
137	Director	Externato Liceal de Albergaria dos Doze	Middle School and Lower Secondary School	Portugal	Rural	NO	https://www.facebook.com/p/Externato-Liceal-Albergaria-dos-Doze-100049401045962/
138	Director	Agrupamento de Escolas de Murça	Preschool to Secondary School	Portugal	Rural	NO	https://www.avmurca.org/

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139	Director	Escola Profissional de Desenvolvimento Rural do Rodo	Professional School (Secondary School level)	Portugal	Rural	YES	https://eprodo.pt/
140	Director	Agrupamento de Escolas Leonardo Coimbra Filho, Porto	Preschool to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	YES	https://aeleonardocoimbra.net/portal/
141	Director	Centro de Educação Integral	Preschool to Secondary School	Portugal	Rural	NO	https://www.centro-edu-integral.pt/
142	Director	Escola de Segunda Oportunidade de Valongo	Second Chance School	Portugal	Urban	YES	https://novo.aermesinde.net/wp/tempo-de-natal-escola-segunda-oportunidade-de-valongo/
143	Teacher	Agrupamento de Escolas Francisco de Holanda	Preschool to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	http://www.aefh.pt/
144	Teacher	Agrupamento de Escolas Infante D. Henrique	Preschool to Lower Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://www.aeidh.pt/
145	Director	Colégio Nova Encosta	Primary to Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://www.colegionovaencosta.pt/
146	Teacher	Escola Básica do 2º e 3º Ciclo Dr. Horácio Bento de Gouveia	Middle School and Lower Secondary School	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://hbg.pt/
147	Director	Colégio de Santa Teresa de Jesus	Preschool to Lower	Portugal	Urban	NO	https://www.colegiostj.com/

			Secondary School				
148	English teacher. European projects expert teacher.	IES "Reino Aftasi" (Badajoz)	Secondary general education. Secondary vocational education. Tertiary education (full-time)-vocational education-	Spain	Urban	YES	https://reinoaftasi.es/
149	English teacher. European projects expert teacher.	CEIP "Francisco Montero de Espinosa" (Almendralejo)	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://cpfmespinosa.educarex.es/
150	Guidance teacher. Member of the management team	COL "Virgen de Guadalupe - Fundación Loyola- "	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education. Secondary general education. Secondary vocational education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://fundacionloyola.com/vguadalupe/

			Tertiary education (full-time)-vocational education-.				
151	Head manager, Community educator	IES "Turgalium"	Secondary general education. Secondary vocational education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://iesturgalium.educarex.es/
152	Head manager,	CEIP Cerro de Reyes - Badajoz	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://cpcerrodereyes.educarex.es/
153	Head manager,	CEIP Gabriel y Galán - Cáceres	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://cpgabrielygalan.educarex.es/
154	Head manager,	CEIP El Pozón - Naval Moral de la Mata	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://cpelpozon.educarex.es/
155	Head manager,	CEIP La Paz – Plasencia	Early childhood education 3-5.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://cplapazplasen.educarex.es/

			Primary education				
156	Head manager,	CEIP Pedro de Vilallonga Cánovas - San Vicente de Alcántara	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://cppvcanovas.educar.ex.es/
157	Head manager,	CEIP Ntra. Sra de Fátima - Badajoz	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://cpnsdefatimabad.educarex.es/
158	Head manager,	CEIP Juan Güell - Talayuela	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://ceipjuanguell.educar.ex.es/
159	Head manager,	IES San Fernando - Badajoz	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://iessanfernando.educarex.es/
160	Head manager,	IES Albarregas - Mérida	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://sites.google.com/iesalbarregas.es/portada/inicio
161	Head manager,	IES Maestro Gonzalo Korreas - Jaraíz de la Vera, Cáceres	Secondary general education. Secondary vocational education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://iesmgkorreas.educar.ex.es/

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162	Head manager,	IES CAROLINA CORONADO - Almendralejo	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://iesccoronado.educarex.es/
163	Head manager,	IES San Roque- Badajoz	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://iessanroque.educarex.es/
164	Head manager,	IES Javier García Téllez- Cáceres	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://iesjgarciatellez.educarex.es/
165	Head manager, community educator	IES Universidad Laboral - Cáceres	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://iesunivlaboral.educarex.es/
166	Head manager,	IES Bioclimático	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://sites.google.com/educarex.es/redes-para-el-bienestar/inicio
167	Head manager,	CEIP San Pedro de Alcántara (Badajoz)	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://sites.google.com/educarex.es/ceipsanpedrodealcantarabadajoz/inicio
168	Head manager,	IESO MARIANO BARBACID (Solana de los Barros)	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kfwOWAkpdoQ
169	Head manager,	IES CAMPOS DE SAN ROQUE (Valverde de Leganés)	secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://sites.google.com/educarex.es/orientacion-y-tutoria/acomodo-emocional
170	Head manager,	IES EMÉRITA (Mérida)	Secondary general education.	Spain	Urban	YES	https://sites.google.com/educarex.es/filosofiaparaintere

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			Secondary vocational education.				sados/proyecto-salud-mental?pli=1
171	Head manager,	CEIP SAN JOSÉ DE CALASANZ (Fuente del Maestro)	Early childhood education 3-5. Primary education	Spain	Urban	YES	https://sites.google.com/view/saludmentalsjc/inicio

Annex II: CoS Recruitment Fact Sheet

LET'S CARE

EC - PROJECT NUMBER: 101059425

WP1: LET'S CARE: BUILDING UP A COMMUNITY

COMMUNITY OF SCHOOLS (CoS)

Secure attachment relationships play an important protective role against the intergenerational transmission of social exclusion, not only at early stages but at all school levels. LET'S CARE aims to comprehensively understand and improve the caring dimension of educational inclusion and school success.

The project's main objective is to identify determinants affecting student security as a root cause of underachievement, disengagement and school dropout at 4 different ecological levels: individual, relational, community and political. LET'S CARE will create a theoretical and practical framework to foster Safe Learning, Safe Teaching, Safe Schools and Safe Education in each level as an approach to break the chain of transgenerational transmission of educational and social exclusion. This approach will generate lower rates of school failure, poor learning outcomes and early school leaving.

The main proposal breakthrough is based on considering a relational response to educational exclusion and inequality, resulting in a model for understanding the importance of security to address underachievement and early dropout and a relational approach to inclusive practices at school that will be translated into tools, recommendations and guidelines for action, from ECEC to secondary and Second Chance schools.

For this purpose, after a wide literature review, the project will organise a data collection phase at schools using in-depth interviews, life histories, focus groups, school ethnographies and data surveys. Finally, an implementation phase will take place giving participants the opportunity to explore project's tools as: Safe Teaching Training Program, Safe School Label or Safe Learning e-portfolio.

In summary, a multilevel, multistage and intersectional research, exploring different European educational contexts, will be implemented, including 120 schools, 18,000 students, and 2,400

teachers from 6 European countries (Poland, Lithuania, Spain, Italy, Bulgaria and Portugal) in 4 schools' stages, with special attention to multi-disadvantaged learners.

LET'S CARE, supported by an expert consortium, will implement a holistic methodological approach, including cocreation mechanisms, and will translate research findings into political approach, through formulation of novel evidence-based policy recommendations, raising awareness on safe/caring schools, combating social exclusion of disadvantaged learners.

Within the LET'S CARE project, **3 schools per country** (total 18 schools) will participate in the **Community of Schools (CoS)**. This community will meet online, with English as the working language. These 18 schools will be involved in the project's model validation, qualitative data collection and piloting phases. As a result of this participation, Cos members:

- Will be trained in different methodologies related to LET'S CARE concepts and participatory approaches.
- Will be an active part of LET'S CARE resources as Safe Teaching Practices wiki-database, aimed at generating and supporting collaborative dynamics of self and peer observation, and Safe Teaching, in order to improve the safety and care of students in relation with their teachers, offering the possibility of sharing practices and validating peer practices.
- Will have access to Safe Learning e-portfolio tool, a longitudinal student monitor tool, useful for school guidance, orientation and tutorial action to follow up and help the transition process between teachers, schools' stages or schools. This tool will be based on the detection of risk and resilience indicators of Safe Learning, school achievement and engagement.
- Will have access to Safe Teaching Training program, a training program comprised of formative materials adapted to each school stage and focused on the training of teachers and school boards in terms of safety.

From March 2023, **20 schools per country will be selected to participate in the fieldwork** (online questionnaire and ethnographic research to be carried out in schools). To ensure the coordination of schools per country, two coordinators per country will be appointed (12 in total), who will be part of the **National Coordinators Board or NCB**, one of them will be a member of LET'S CARE team, and the other one will be **a teacher selected to represent the national school community of the country**. The NCB will meet online (working language will be English). NCB will be directly involved in different issues, such as select and invite a maximum of 120 schools (20 per country), the project's model

validation or adaptation and implementation of the data collection process. NCB members will be trained during the project in different project tools such as trainer of Safe Teaching Training Program.

The **actions to be developed** are as follows:

In the **2022/23 academic year:**

- One focus group with teachers (5- 7 teachers per school)

In the **2023/2024 academic year:**

- Teachers of focus group will participate in a professional community of practice. They reflect and observe their educational practice to systematise and publish them in the HUB. These teachers will publish and exchange their practices through the HUB and other spaces as journals and conferences.

In the **2024-2025 academic year:**

- 150 students and 20 teachers will participate in a data collection survey.
- (only for Italy, Poland, and Spain) A small pre-test of LET'S CARE tools piloting will be carried out.

In the 2025-2026 academic year:

- (Only in Extremadura) The e-profile tool will be piloted
- (Only for Italy, Poland and Spain) A group of 6-7 teachers per-country will participate in the piloting of the LET'S CARE Teacher Training Program, also with the opportunity to give feedback.
- The school headmaster of 10 schools per country will be trained to use the Safe School Label to check the assessment checklist and give feedback.